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Land use and land cover changes: implications for malaria elimination

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Land use and land cover changes: implications for malaria elimination

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Contents

Executive summary	3
1. Land use and land cover changes	5
1.1 Land use and land cover changes globally	5
Box 1. Defining forests	6
1.2 Land use and land cover change and malaria transmission	8
2. LULCC impacts on vector biology	10
2.1 Forest disturbance and vector populations	10
2.1.1 Larval habitats and deforestation	10
2.1.2 Changes in species composition and ecological adaptation	11
2.2 Agricultural practices and vector populations	13
2.3 Hydrological infrastructure and vector populations	14
2.4 Environmental management and vector populations	15
3. Land use and human populations	17
3.1 Influx of populations into endemic areas	17
3.2 Population migration between areas of different malaria endemicity	18
3.3 Occupational changes and risk behaviours	19
3.4 Socioeconomic development	19
Box 2. Case study: Malaria in Venezuela: economic effects on deforestation, reductions in health services and malaria transmission	20
4. Wildlife reservoirs	22
4.1 Plasmodium knowlesi in Southeast Asia	23
Box 3. Identifying relevant spatial scales to assess linkages between land use and disease risks ...	26
4.2 P. simium and P. brasilianum in South America	27
5. Monitoring land use change to assess relationships with malaria	28
5.1 Satellite-based remote sensing	28
5.2 Aerial imagery	29
5.3 Habitat configuration	30

5.4 Identifying environmental risk factors for malaria	31
6. Malaria elimination and LULCC.....	32

Executive summary

Land use and land cover changes (LULCC) are one of the main forms of anthropogenic environmental changes, transforming over 75% of ice-free land on the planet. Land cover describes the physical and biological cover of terrestrial surfaces while land use refers to the human modification and management of land areas. LULCC, such as deforestation, agricultural expansion and infrastructure development, have profound impacts on ecological systems, altering the distribution of people, animal reservoirs of disease and insect vectors that can transmit infections. These alterations have been linked to changes in the transmission and geographical distribution of malaria and other vector-borne diseases globally, either increasing or decreasing malaria risks in different settings depending on a range of environmental, biological and social factors.

LULCC such as deforestation can lead to physical changes in the environment, affecting suitability for anopheline mosquito breeding sites. In sites such as the Amazon and Southeast Asia, forest clearing has been linked to increases in suitable vector habitats which are in closer proximity with people. These habitat changes may also lead to disruptions of existing ecological systems, such as initial decreases in vector densities followed by colonisation by more efficient species. Similarly, agriculture and expansion of irrigation can create environmental conditions leading to changes in vector populations. The effects of these environmental changes can be further amplified by wildlife reservoirs. Emergence of simian malarias in South America and Southeast Asia highlight how increased contact between people, wildlife hosts and mosquito vectors can lead to new public health issues and challenge malaria elimination efforts.

LULCC also impact the human populations at risk. Development of new land areas is often followed by influxes of susceptible populations into malaria endemic areas. Similarly, occupational practices such as gold mining, forest clearing and farming may change risk behaviours of these populations and contribute to increased exposure to vectors during peak biting times. Human disease risks are modified by wider social and economic contexts; while economic prosperity from agricultural development can lead to better housing conditions and access to health care, weakened social structures and disease control measures in forest frontier regions can increase malaria burdens.

Spatially and temporally accurate data on both malaria and land cover is needed to monitor disease risks in a changing landscape. Satellite-based remote sensing data is increasingly accessible to track global land cover changes, such as deforestation. These data can be supplemented by new

technologies such as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs or drones), used to map areas of interest with high spatial and temporal resolution. Data on land cover, land use and habitat configuration can be integrated with spatially explicit malaria data to identify risk factors for disease and predict future malaria burdens. This continued development and use of GPS and satellite data to track habitat disturbance, human space use and changes in anopheline populations should be utilised to inform decisions. Detailed data on human, mosquito and other host distributions relative to land cover and land use factors collected in a consistent method is needed to fully understand the long-term consequences of these changing environments.

The impacts of LULCC on malaria transmission are highly complex and context specific; environmental and demographic changes within a specific setting may lead to increases or decreases in malaria risks. Establishing a direct link between LULCC and malaria transmission is often difficult, given the interactions between the environment and intrinsic factors such as species composition and ecology, demographic changes influencing socioeconomic status, risk behaviours and access to control measures. Further research is needed to identify the most informative available environmental data to integrate with epidemiological datasets to assess how LULCC affects malaria transmission. This could allow identification of high risk areas and populations as well as implementation of spatially targeted interventions such as environmental management and malaria control plans for specific planned developments.

1. Land use and land cover changes

1.1 Land use and land cover changes globally

Land use and land cover changes (LULCC) are one of the main causes of global environmental change and contribute to a quarter of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Land cover refers to the physical and biological cover of terrestrial surfaces, such as water, soil, vegetation and infrastructure, while land use refers to the human management and activities which modify land surface processes [2]. Although people have transformed landscapes since the development of agriculture in prehistoric times, the extensive changes in the past 300 years following the Industrial Revolution have been unprecedented, leading to this era being termed the Anthropocene [3]. While agricultural land occupied less than 2% of global ice-free land prior to 1000 AD, this percentage increased to over 4% in 1700 AD to 35% in 2000 AD [4]. Today, over 75% of Earth's ice-free land has been altered by human residence and land use [5]. Driven by agricultural expansion, population growth and resource extraction, these extensive changes fundamentally alter ecological and environmental processes at local, regional and global scales [6].

Deforestation remains one of the main contributors to global LULCC. Changes to forest cover are particularly pronounced in tropical areas, where over 80% of new agricultural land was cleared from tropical rainforests between 1980 and 2000 and an estimated 2100 km² of forests were lost per year between 2000 and 2012 [7, 8]. Rates of tropical deforestation continue to increase despite considerable international attention, with the largest areas of forest loss observed in 2016 followed by 2017 [9]. Levels of forest disturbance range from large-scale clear cutting and burning to selective extraction and community forest management. Forest degradation may be monitored by changes in canopy cover, above ground biomass, forest gaps and fragmentation and proxies of forest activities, such as road networks and other infrastructure [10]. As well as forest loss, land use changes may also include reforestation, the re-establishment of forest on land that recently had forest cover, and afforestation, establishment of forest on land which historically did not contain forest [1].

Box 1. Defining forests

The many international agencies, governments and other organisations conducting forestry assessments have led to a wide range of definitions for forest. The 2015 Forest Resources Assessment attempted to standardise definitions of forest, defining forest as “land spanning more than 0.5 hectares with trees higher than 5 metres and a canopy cover of more than 10 percent, or trees able to reach these thresholds *in situ*.” This definition excludes land predominantly under agricultural or urban land use and includes areas with mangroves, rubberwood, oak, Christmas tree plantations, bamboo and palms meeting the height and canopy cover threshold [11].

Substantial heterogeneities exist within this broad definition of forest. Primary forests are defined as natural forests of native species with no visible indication of human activities and undisturbed ecological processes [11]. These forests may additionally be defined in terms of “intactness”; while there is no set threshold or definition for intact forests, this typically refers to a primary forest of a certain area undisturbed by human land use, infrastructure or industrial activities [12]. In contrast, secondary forests typically refer to the regrowth of forests following human disturbance. These may be classed in terms of canopy disturbance or ecological succession stages as vegetation and shrubland grow in cleared areas and progress to secondary forests with different levels of maturity (Figure 1). Regionally, types of forests may be further defined by predominant species, soil types, management practices or other characteristics. In many tropical regions, natural forest losses have been driven by mono-crop agro-forestry such as oil palm, pulpwood and rubber [13, 14]. Substantial variations exist in the management and sustainability of these plantations and their classification as forests remains debated.

Figure 1. Stages of forest succession

Much of this deforestation is driven by the expansion of lands for commodity crops as population growth and increased consumption levels lead to rising demands for agricultural products [15]. Between 1970 and 2010, there has been a 1.4-fold increase in the number of livestock and an 18.4% increase in daily per capita food availability globally [1]. However, increased productivity and industrialisation has meant this increase in the amount of food produced is not always accompanied by corresponding increases in land area but rather the application of new management techniques, such as irrigation and fertilisers [16]. For example, there was a 73% increase in the area of irrigated land between 1970 and 2010 [11]. Global biofuel production is also increasing rapidly, growing 19.4% per year globally between 2004 and 2011, with an expansion of 33.2 million hectares for oilseeds globally, further driving agricultural expansion [17].

As the need for resources drive LULCC, the increased availability of these resources supports population growth. The world population is projected to grow from 7.6 billion people in 2017 to over 11 billion in 2100 [18]. Over 70% of global populations are projected to live in urban areas by 2050, necessitating the development of roads, waterways and other infrastructure to support urban centres [19]. Although urbanisation is often correlated with increased economic development and access to better health care, these landscape changes may create new challenges and drive travel, trade and other land use changes across the planet.

The causes for land use change are multifactorial, with underlying political, institutional and economic factors driving agricultural expansion, resource extraction and infrastructure development [20]. For example, while rapid and extensive deforestation occurred in Indonesia between 2000 and 2012, the commitment to a forest moratorium policy protecting forests and peatlands as part of the Indonesian Intended Nationally Determined Contributions to mitigate global climate change led to substantial decreases in forest loss in 2017 [9, 21, 22]. Conversely, economic and political policies may have unintended implications for deforestation and conservation. Peace agreements between the Colombian government and armed groups led to large increases in land colonisation in previously inaccessible areas of the Andean-Amazonian foothills of Colombia; deforestation has been further amplified by governmental programs building roads and fostering extractive and ranching industries [23]. United States drug policies have led to what is termed narco-deforestation, extensive forest loss in Central America fuelled by the development of landing strips, need to launder money and influxes of cash and weapons from the global narcotics trade [24]. These complex economic and social forces driving land use change may have unintended consequences for ecological systems and human well-being.

1.2 Land use and land cover change and malaria transmission

One of the effects of these anthropogenic environmental changes are impacts on infectious disease emergence and transmission [25-27]. Deforestation, urbanisation and agricultural expansion affect the distribution of people, animal reservoirs and disease vectors, impacting infectious disease risks [28-30]. These have been linked to altered dynamics and geographical distribution of malaria and other vector-borne diseases globally [31-33]. LULCC can modify the physical environment and disrupt existing ecosystems, impacting vector and reservoir populations, while simultaneously contributing to social and demographic changes which may either increase or decrease malaria risks [33]. As many of the most pronounced and intensive LULCC occur in tropical areas, understanding how these ecological changes driven by human activity modify malaria epidemiology is vital to predicting future disease risks and designing malaria control and elimination programmes.

Table 1: Examples of effects of land use change on potential malaria risks

Environmental changes		References
Deforestation	Increases in anopheline larval breeding sites in response to forest clearing in the Amazon	[34]
	Initial decreases in vector densities followed by colonisation by more efficient malaria vectors	[31, 35]
	Changes in vector habitat suitability linked with forest disturbance	[36, 37]
	Changes in ecological structure and biodiversity increasing or decreasing vector densities, availability of blood meals and resulting disease risks	[38-40]
Agricultural expansion	Effects of irrigation systems	[41, 42]
	Expansion of rubber and rice paddies associated with increases in anopheline densities	[33, 43]
Socio-demographic changes		
Population at risk	Influx of susceptible populations into endemic areas in response to increased economic opportunity	[44, 45]
	Increase and movement of migrant worker populations in the Amazon and Southeast Asia	[46, 47]
	Occupational changes, such as forestry and extraction activities bringing people into vector habitats	[48, 49]
Socioeconomic status	Increased income following agricultural development leading to decrease in malaria risk	[50]
	Improved housing structure due to development reducing malaria risks	[51, 52]
Wildlife reservoirs		
Origin of malaria	<i>P. falciparum</i> originated from non-human primates	[53]
Spatial overlap with wildlife hosts	Increased contact between people and non-human primates hypothesised as main driver of human infections with <i>P. knowlesi</i> and <i>P. cynomolgi</i> in Asia and <i>P. simium</i> and <i>P. brasilianum</i> in South America	[54-57]
Maintenance of malaria infections	Human malaria species circulating in great apes and gorillas in West and Central Africa	[58, 59]

2. LULCC impacts on vector biology

2.1 Forest disturbance and vector populations

Deforestation and landscape changes can impact the species composition and abundance of vector populations. Ecological changes in soil, sunlight cover, vegetation type, development of water pockets and water temperature, can alter breeding conditions for *Anopheles* malaria vectors. Deforestation can reduce shaded water bodies, the preferred breeding habitats of particular anopheline species. Alternatively, *Anopheles* species thrive when water bodies sunlight exposure rises, significantly increasing larval survivorship, adult productivity, net reproductive fitness, intrinsic growth rate and biting frequency via shortened gonotrophic cycles, all of which affect vectorial capacity [33]. Other environmental and climatic changes due to deforestation may favour survival of different anopheles species enabling sustained seasonal malaria transmission. In some cases, elimination of one species as a result of deforestation might be followed by replacement by another *Anopheles* species [31].

2.1.1 Larval habitats and deforestation

Associations between levels of forest disturbance and vector breeding sites and densities are widely described in Southeast Asia and the Western Pacific. Many species of highly efficient forest vectors occur within this region and forest fringe and deforested areas provide adequate breeding sites for these vectors. Among the diversity of deep and near forest main vectors, *An. dirus* stands out with its ecological plasticity, broad geographical range and vectorial efficiency [31]. Within an anthropogenic disturbance gradient in Sabah, Malaysia, the number of *Anopheles* catches was greater in both lightly and heavily modified forest than in the unmodified primary forest, with wheel tracks in logged areas particularly providing plentiful mosquito breeding sites [36]. Forest disturbance had the combined effect on vector populations of increasing abundance and human landing rates at ground level [36, 60].

Within the Amazon, deforestation also resulted in increased larval breeding sites and corresponding increases in malaria incidence [34]. Human population growth as a result of oil exploration, the cocoa trade and rural expansion in the northern Peruvian Amazon increased pressure on forested land, with an estimated 4,257 hectares of forest cleared annually between 1983 to 1995 [34]. Low malaria prevalence in the region due to eradication programs in the 1960s was disturbed by

accelerated deforestation with a dramatic increase in *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*. From 1992 to 1997, a 4-fold increase in malaria cases was recorded in Peru with a 50-fold increase within the Loreto Department [61].

High transmission zones included river basin communities and communities along the first asphalt extension of the Iquitos-Nauta road. The rapid emergence of epidemic malaria in Loreto department paralleled the increase in *An. darlingi*, which was not found in the area in 1991 [61]. Increased larval breeding sites favourable to *An. darlingi* in the Peruvian amazon, were situated closer to ecologically altered landscapes (shrub, grass and crop land) and further from forest. Areas with less than 10% secondary growth had a 1-2% probability of having *An. darlingi*, in striking comparison to areas with more than 40% secondary growth which had a 12-20% probability of *An. darlingi* presence [34]. Additionally, large ponds containing algae were also found to be conducive to larval breeding. Habitat alteration resulting from cycles of deforestation of land adjacent to village areas (swidden farming), with land left to fallow and regrow after becoming infertile before subsequently clearing and replanting, is common amongst non-nomadic farmer settlements in the Amazon basin; the resulting conditions created by these human settlements are especially attractive for the predominant malaria vector [34].

However, in some sites, forest disturbance may actually reduce malaria risks. For example, in African sites where the deep forest species *An. nili* is the main vector, deforestation leads to modest reductions in malaria transmission [31]. Alternatively, in other African sites, deforestation can create habitats for non-forest efficient vectors. In Nigeria, forest loss was demonstrated to have a large impact on malaria risks, with each standard deviation of forest loss corresponding to an almost 5% increase in malaria in children under 5 [62]. A study in the Democratic Republic of Congo similarly found deforestation and agricultural expansion led to an increase in malaria prevalence in children; these land use changes were associated with increases of indoor biting rates of the malaria vector *An. gambiae sensu lato* [63].

2.1.2 Changes in species composition and ecological adaptation

Forest disturbance can also impact species composition, opening larval habitat opportunities and creating conditions in which colonist mosquitoes can thrive. Deforestation may initially deplete deep forest vectors but invasion by other efficient vectors may happen in some localities [31]. Counterintuitively, the abundance of both colonist (disturbance-tolerant) and climax (disturbance-

intolerant) anopheline mosquitoes species increased in disturbed forests in Panama [37]. *An.albimanus*, a colonist species, co-existed at the landscape scale with two climax species, *An.oswaldoi* and *An.triannulatus*, but not at the larval habitat scale. Interestingly, these climax species co-occurred at the larval habitat but their abundances were lower than *An.albimanus*. In this setting, the likelihood of colonist-vector species occurrence was most prominent at highly disturbed forest sites and decreased markedly in relatively undisturbed forest [37]. These impacts on species abundance influence contact rates with hosts and pathogen transmission, with colonist species found to be more likely to transmit pathogens than climax species.

As well, in the Peruvian Amazon, displacement of other anophelines such as *An.benarrochi*, *An.oswaldoi* and *An.mattogrossensis* by *An. darlingi* occurred in the 1990s. The latter became the primary vector in the region and established itself as the most abundant riverine species. In the peri-Quitos area of the Loreto Department, *An.darlingi* re-emergence in 1996 along a concomitant malaria epidemic that reached 150,000 cases in 1997 was followed by fluctuations in cases from 22,406 in 2000 to 60,168 in 2014. A recent study indicates that *An.darlingi* in Loreto underwent genetic population replacement after 2006 with two distinct subpopulations differently distributed within highway and river habitats. Significant effects of forest cover and habitat on human biting rate in 2012-2014 *An.darlingi* collections translated into threefold higher entomological inoculation rates in peri-domestic riverine sites than in highway settlements. These results were associated with available host biomass [64]. Findings provide evidence of ecological adaptation and apparent early stage differentiation caused by anthropogenic alterations.

In a study conducted in 2005 in Cambodia, mosquito collections were carried out in forest camps and nearby villages where the majority of inhabitants were engaged in forest-related work activities such as agriculture, logging and hunting. Forest in the area was scattered and fragmented. Vector complex densities were similar between forest and village and both known primary and secondary vectors were present in 82.9% of collections [35]. Besides the primary anthropophilic vectors *An.minimus* and *An.dirus*, outdoor and early biting behaviours in secondary vectors could sustain malaria transmission in such fragmented areas due to the higher contact rate between inhabitants and anophelids. In this setting, full deforestation is expected to lower primary vector but increase secondary vector densities, with Cambodia reporting substantial decreases in both national malaria prevalence and forest cover [35, 65].

2.2 Agricultural practices and vector populations

Agriculture has also been associated with changes in *Anopheles* densities, varying by species and between types of agriculture and localities, with complex associations reported between development projects and changes in mosquito density. Vector populations may be affected by factors such as the habitats created by planted crops, use of water for irrigation, applications of pesticides or changes in host availability.

Rubber plantations, containing planted rubber trees with high humidity and lower temperatures under canopy cover, often provide ideal environments for malaria vectors. Rubber plantations additionally contain a wide range of larval breeding habitats, from slow running streams, puddles and pools to latex-collecting cups and water-storage containers, all supporting a diverse vector fauna. Since the first accounts of malaria in Malaysian rubber plantations, regular malaria outbreaks have been reported across Southeast Asia's rubber plantations [43]. Site and time of the year influence predominant species in rubber plantations. For example, in Thailand, *An.dirus* was the primary vector during the dry season with *An.minimus* as a secondary vector; while *An.dirus*, *An.minimus*, *An.maculatus* and *An.aconitus* were the main vectors during the rainy season. As 90% of the global demand in rubber is met by the expansion of rubber plantations in South East Asia, with an expanding migrant workforce subject to high vector exposure, marked declines in malaria mortality in this region might be jeopardised by the rubber boom [43].

Alternatively, the introduction of other crop species or farming practices can alter vector species composition. In Thailand in the 1970s, development of cassava and sugarcane plantations led to increases in malaria risks. While these agricultural changes decreased the density of the shade-loving species *An. dirus*, the modified landscape provided ideal breeding conditions for the sun-loving *An. minimus* and resulted in an increase in malaria transmission among resettled cultivators [33]. Other agricultural methods such as slash and burn techniques similarly lead to deep shade elimination, changes in the acidity and chemical composition of the soil, creation of new breeding sites in the forest fringes and higher host exposure, promoting the establishment of anopheline populations [31]. In Panama, possible competitive displacement of *An. oswaldoi* and *An. triannulatus* by *An.albimanus* has been suggested with greater abundance of the colonist species observed at the larval habitat level [37].

Irrigated cultivation of cereal crops also provides ideal larval habitats for malaria mosquitoes, sheltering larvae from abiotic and biotic threats and providing nutrients such as shed pollen, detritus and microorganisms. Agro-ecosystems derived from irrigated rice cultivation can create permanent habitats for mosquito larvae [66]. Prolongation of the breeding season of *An. aconitus* caused by rice cultivation and its linked irrigation systems in Indonesia, resulted in an increase of malaria incidence [33]. In sub-Saharan Africa, initiatives to systematically increase regions under irrigated rice cultivations have resulted in a rise in prevalence of the malaria vector, *An. arabiensis*. Agronomic practices in rice such as fertilizer and insecticide use, can increase available nutrients and create predator-free habitats, respectively, thereby augmenting larval density. Furthermore, a recent study showed that gravid *An. arabiensis* are attracted to the odour of rice, acting as a cue for oviposition site selection [66]. Hence, female mosquitoes provide their offspring with selective advantages by targeting rice paddies as breeding sites. The impact of increased vector densities on malaria transmission is uncertain; in many cases, it may depend on socioeconomic factors and public health programmes associated with agricultural expansion [67].

2.3 Hydrological infrastructure and vector populations

Increases in malaria transmission resulting from establishment of water projects is affected not only by contextual determinants of malaria but also by specific habitat preferences of the anopheles species involved [42]. As with the impact of other LULCC, contextual determinants, including epidemiologic setting, socioeconomic factors, vector management, health seeking behaviour and possibility of settlement dependant on topography, vary with each irrigation project. Environmental factors impacting anopheline preferences include exposure to sunlight, turbidity of the water, presence of vegetation, pH, and nitrate and phosphate concentrations of the water, and are specific for the irrigation project and its shoreline.

A substantial body of literature documents increased malaria incidence following development of irrigation systems and increased mosquito density in many parts of the world [42]. Introduction of irrigation in northern Afghanistan in the 1960s for rice, cotton and watermelon cultivation, resulted in a 4-fold increase in malaria cases in some locations. Overflows of irrigation ditches created ideal habitats for *An. pulcherrimus* and *An. hyrcanus groups* [33]. Recently, food security and economic development challenges in sub-Saharan Africa have encouraged large dam construction and irrigation schemes; the ecological transformation from these projects can substantially change the malaria risk for communities in their vicinity. In sub-Saharan Africa, the potential impacts of dams

were analysed by mapping an extensive set of existing and planned dams against the malaria stability index, using the Malaria Atlas Project (MAP) and WorldPop databases [68]. Findings confirm the major malaria impact of large dams in areas of unstable transmission either by intensification or seasonal to perennial changes on malaria transmission [42, 68]. Existing large dams were predicted to increase the risk of malaria for around 15 million people, adding more than 1 million cases annually to the malaria burden in the region, with an additional 50,000 cases per year resulting from planned dams. The creation of new mosquito breeding sites, demographic changes and changing human-vector-parasite contact patterns brought about by these dams could confound current malaria control efforts towards reduction and elimination in Africa and contribute substantially to the cumulative malaria burden.

Figure 2. Map showing spatial distribution of existing and planned dams in Africa with respect to the 2010 malaria stability indexing (from Kibret et al. [22])

2.4 Environmental management and vector populations

In some cases, deliberate environmental management can be utilised to minimise the impact of LULCC and reduce malaria transmission overall. Plans to reduce vector-parasite contact generally comprise of three approaches: environmental modification on land, water or vegetation with long-lasting effects for vector habitat reduction; environmental manipulation that generates unfavourable temporary conditions for vectors; and modification of human habitation to reduce exposure to vectors. In a systematic review that emphasized the effectiveness of environmental management interventions for decreasing malaria morbidity and mortality, 16 studies that applied environmental modification and 8 studies that modified human habitation, the risk ratio of malaria was reduced by 88% and 79.5%, respectively [69].

For example, cacao plantations under nurse trees in Trinidad generated ideal breeding sites within epiphytic bromeliads for *An. bellator*, the main local malaria vector. Control of the resulting malaria epidemic was achieved through environmental manipulation with the modification of plantation techniques [33]. With the intent of preventing malaria epidemics, environmental manipulation has been proposed in Panama and other Latin American countries by increasing forest cover recovery in highly disturbed deforested areas, thus favouring the prevalence of auxiliary over primary vectors [37].

One of the most successful large scale environmental modification interventions was during the construction of the Panama Canal. In 1878, this construction was halted due to engineering challenges, yellow fever and malaria and the resulting deaths amongst workers. Sanitation improvements allowed continuation of the project, including implementation of temporary and permanent drainage infrastructure and vegetation management [69]. Malaria incidence amid employees decreased from 821 per 1000 in 1906 to 14 per 1000 in 1917.

Other engineering approaches include drainage, river boundary modification, filling of swamps and other stagnant water bodies. Utilisation of intermittent irrigation in African rice fields has greatly reduced anopheline densities and increased rice yields while construction of several types of siphons and small dams in Sri Lanka and Malaysia's rivers and streams eliminated mosquito breeding habitats. Environmental management interventions in the reservoirs of the Tennessee River Valley including an integrated operating rule for water fluctuation cycles, reduced anopheles breeding sites significantly [69]. Integrated malaria control implemented with effective water management measures is essential in the proximity of irrigation or dam sites within unstable malaria endemic areas to prevent increases in malaria transmission [42, 68, 69].

3. Land use and human populations

As land use refers to the human management of terrestrial surfaces, LULCC is intricately linked with the distribution, movement and quality of life of human populations. These movements of human populations have shaped pathogen evolution and spread; recent analysis of mitochondrial genomes from global samples traced the introduction of malaria parasites into the New World via human migration. Transcontinental gene flow patterns differ among malaria species, with *P. falciparum* outspread from Africa to Eurasia and the Pacific alongside human colonisation. Further human migration from Africa as a result of the slave trade brought *P. falciparum* to the Americas with enslaved Africans being captured from coastal, central and east locations. Phylogenetic analysis reveals a global geographical structure of *P. falciparum* associated with independent colonisation episodes [70]. Successive migratory waves in the Americas explain the extensive genetic diversity found in *P. vivax* current populations, with significant gene flow from Africa and South Asia and added contribution from Melanesian lineages. Findings support a recent transfer of *P. simium*, a *P. vivax*-like parasite, from humans to monkeys in the Atlantic Brazilian forest which would explain the low diversity of recovered lineages, in tandem with the late significant human encroachment into this ecosystem [57, 70].

3.1 Influx of populations into endemic areas

One of these consequences of LULCC changes is the influx immunologically naïve populations into endemic areas. The impact of these population changes has been well described in the Brazilian Amazon, where policies encouraging occupation of the Amazon in the 1970s were linked to the explosive increase in malaria cases. Within Brazil, the number of malaria cases annually increased from a total of 8,000 cases prior to the explicit government policy to up to 615,000 in the year 2000. Of these cases, 99% of all malaria cases after 1990 were recorded in Brazil's Amazon and 92% of cases in other regions of the country were related to individuals who had been in the Amazon recently [45].

Cattle ranching and agricultural colonisation, small-scale gold mining and development of settlements have been associated with malaria risks within the Amazon. Termed "frontier malaria," early stages of forest clearance are linked with changes in human exposure risks and creation of vector breeding sites [49]. Risks of malaria are often highest during the initial stages of land clearing

and settlement, decreasing with urbanisation, agricultural expansion and increased socioeconomic status [71].

These frontier communities are often characterised by weak social institutions and limited health care, further contributing to disease risks [72]. In the Amazon, dramatic increases in population accompanied by similar increases in malaria cases were characterised by irregular geographical distribution of cases and absence of coordinated mitigation strategies. Political and economic factors influenced behaviours which put ecosystems under intense and sudden pressures, generating frontier malaria with complex interactions at three scales. First, ecological changes favourable to *An.darlingi* larvae and subsequent high vector densities of the predominant neotropical vector translated into high human exposure among non-immune populations that engage in risk behaviours related to outdoor work. Second, poor community level cohesion was characterised by sparsely available health services, high influx of temporary workers, poor housing quality and weak institutions. Third, as there was no central planning of new settlements, migration was disorganised and no malaria protective measures were enacted [49].

3.2 Population migration between areas of different malaria endemicity

Beyond geographical range of mosquitoes, malaria spread can be augmented by infected travellers that move regularly between regions with variable intrinsic vector transmission potential (receptivity). Malaria can be imported by individuals visiting endemic areas and returning to their place of residency or infected individuals carrying parasites while visiting other settlements. Within the Brazilian Amazon, proximity and mobility between frontier settlements and activities explain malaria diffusion regionally [45]. Similarly, in the village of Cacao, French Guiana, a recently built road connecting the village with Brazil may have facilitated the movement of carriers from endemic areas. While no cases were reported in the previous 14 years, a *P. vivax* epidemic between 2002 and 2007 affected 43% of the inhabitants and 267 temporary residents to the area [48].

On a national level, individuals may move from more remote malaria endemic areas to urban centres; these movements are often driven by trade and connectivity of different land use areas. In Kenya, analysis of phone records of 15 million individuals over a one-year period revealed national-level travel patterns. While the most malaria infections may be imported into Nairobi, vector scarcity within the capital limits receptivity. In contrast, regional movements within endemic areas, as opposed to movements between more urban distant areas, may contribute most to the importation

and increases in malaria transmission [73]. Data on local, regional and national movements are needed to capture how human migration contributes to malaria spread [74].

3.3 Occupational changes and risk behaviours

LULCC are also accompanied by corresponding changes in occupations and risk behaviours. For example, disturbance of forest to increase farming surface has attracted seasonal workers into ideal vector habitats in French Guiana, where temporal clusters coincided with the rainy season and activities regularly carried out by seasonal workers like deforestation, logging and fruit-picking. Risk behaviours among this migrant worker population such as outside kitchens, agricultural work hours during heightened hematophagous mosquito activity and the absence of repellents or mosquito net use explained the spatial heterogeneity of malaria occurrence during an epidemic in this site [48]. Similar risk behaviours are seen among small scale gold miners in Brazil compounded by the high spatial proximity and mobility of such populations from areas of high malaria prevalence that facilitates diffusion of the parasite [45]. Within Southeast Asia, migrant workers and forest and plantation activities have similarly been identified as risk factors for malaria exposure [35, 75].

3.4 Socioeconomic development

LULCC are frequently motivated by economic factors and can have a correspondingly positive influence on human health. In many places, initial environmental changes are followed by increases in socioeconomic status and improvements in infrastructure and public health services. For example, expansion of irrigation systems in an arid region of India was associated with dramatic increases in malaria risks; however, over time, the economic prosperity from these developments and increased health service availability led to decreased malaria incidence [76]. Models of impacts of deforestation in frontier including socioeconomic factors similarly predict initial increases in malaria transmission followed by decreases due to improved socioeconomic status [71]. Economic development can additionally lead to improvements in housing quality and infrastructure, factors previously associated with decreased risks of malaria [50, 52]. While differing time scales may make untangling environmental and societal impacts on malaria transmission challenging, fully understanding risks of landscape changes requires assessing how these coupled human-environmental systems interact.

Box 2. Case study: Malaria in Venezuela: economic effects on deforestation, reductions in health services and malaria transmission

Economic factors can modify the health impacts of LULCC; in some cases, increased prosperity can reduce malaria burdens despite environmental changes favourable to malaria transmission (e.g. [76]). However, in other situations, the economic pressures contributing to LULCC can simultaneously weaken healthcare institutions creating conditions favourable to malaria resurgence. Within Venezuela, economic collapses have been linked to crippled health systems and rising infectious disease burdens ([77-79]); these same factors have been associated with increases in deforestation due to migration to areas for extractive activities [80].

Although Venezuela had the highest malaria incidence in Latin America prior to 1936, concerted malaria eradication campaigns resulted in the declaration of its northern region as malaria-free by the WHO in 1961 [65, 81]. However, the high rates of inflation, projected to reach 1,000,000% by the end of 2018, lead to a collapse of economic activity, a worsening deterioration of public services including health care, transportation, electricity, water and security, and widespread shortages in addition to weakening malaria control efforts [82]. Malaria cases have risen by 365% between 2000 and 2015, with 319,765 documented cases reported by the end of week 42 in 2017 [78, 83]. Gold mining areas are most affected by malaria: 74% of all 2016 malaria cases in Venezuela occurred in Bolivar state, with 43% of cases concentrated in Sifontes municipality, a gold mining hotspot [65]. These areas, along with parts of the Venezuelan Amazon, are included in the Orinoco Mining Arc, where deforestation is occurring following government decrees opening 12% of the Venezuelan land area for mineral exploitation [84]. In 2017, almost 95% of reported cases occurred within most municipalities of Bolivar, Amazonas and Sucre states, highlighting the spatial heterogeneities of malaria risk [65, 85].

Figure 3. Example of deforestation in Bolivar state, Venezuela from 2000 – 2017 (data obtained from Global Forest Watch, [8])

The increases in malaria transmission around gold mining areas are partly due to changes in vector populations. In a longitudinal entomological and epidemiological study in 1999-2000 carried out in 5 localities of southern Venezuela, transmission was found to be more intense in gold-mining settlements than in indigenous communities. Biting patterns recorded differed between *An. darlingi*, which is active throughout the night and into early morning, and *An. marajoara* which bites predominantly before midnight, supporting an anthropophagy adaptation by *An. darlingi* concurrent with gold mine activity [86]. More recently, in 2009 – 2012, local transmission within malaria foci in the forest ecosystem of South-eastern Venezuela, was shown to be maintained by *An. darlingi* and *An. albitarsis*, with mosquito infection rates of 5.4% and 4%, respectively [87]. Forest disturbance associated with extraction activities appears to expand aquatic vector habitats, particularly *An. albitarsis* breeding sites.

Additionally, the unstable socio-economic and political context drives behavioural changes related to frontier malaria [49, 88]. Economic migrants seeking temporary work in gold mines frequently engage in risk behaviours related to outdoor activities in hyperendemic areas [87]. Malaria risks linked to economic activities was highest among individuals aging 20 – 39 years old; this group

accounted for nearly half of the cases reported in 2017 [85]. The steep increase in malaria cases is further complicated by lapses in vector-control efforts in hyperendemic mining areas increasingly operated illegally [89]. Political and economic factors have influenced factors precipitating the unprecedented increase in malaria cases such as: shortages of insecticides, antimalarials and fuel which impede vector-control and disease treatment, human migrations associated with illegal mining; food insecurity and malnutrition, and poor support for health workers [78]. Indoor residual spraying has significantly dropped from 2.7 million people protected in 2015 to 30,000 people in 2016 [65].

A large proportion of the population has also migrated to bordering countries, overloading frontier health care infrastructure. In 2016, 78% of malaria cases in Brazil and 81% of cases in Colombia, originated in Venezuela [90]. Previously, malaria transmission in Venezuela has been rural but a significant change in the epidemiology of the disease towards urban and peri-urban settings has been described due to highly mobile economic migrants travelling from hotspots [87]. Due to the movement of people from different Venezuela states and bordering countries across the Orinoco Mining Arc the transmission risk has been widened to the whole Venezuelan territory [91].

The socioeconomic forces driving LULCC in Venezuela also drive collapses in health systems and changes in migration and populations at risk. These factors act in combination to not only weaken malaria control within Venezuela, but also hamper malaria elimination efforts in surrounding countries [65, 92]. As documented in the 2017 World Malaria Report, substantial increases in cases in the Americas since 2014 along concurrent initiation of emergency responses are mainly related to the ongoing conflict and resulting humanitarian crisis in Venezuela, with Venezuela accounting for 30% of all malaria cases in the Americas in 2015 [65, 83]. These malaria risks continue to evolve as economic pressures lead to opening of new areas for mining and agriculture. International efforts are needed to address health inequities and establish surveillance and malaria control programmes within high risk areas [92].

4. Wildlife reservoirs

Land use impacts on human and vector populations may be further amplified by wildlife malaria reservoirs. Although the four main human malarias (*P. falciparum*, *P. malariae*, *P. ovale* and *P. vivax*) are widely recognised, zoonotic malaria species such as *P. knowlesi* and *P. simium* are increasingly

being acknowledged as an emerging public health threat [93]. Genetic studies suggest that human malarias such as *P. falciparum* originated from great ape species and these human malarias continue to circulate in great ape and gorilla populations in West and Central Africa [53, 58, 59]. These close evolutionary relationships, coupled with increased spatial overlap between human and non-human primate populations, present future threats of disease emergence and challenges to malaria elimination and control programmes.

4.1 Plasmodium knowlesi in Southeast Asia

P. knowlesi is an emerging malaria species maintained by long and pig-tailed macaques (*Macaca fascicularis* and *M. nemestrina*) and transmitted by the *Anopheles leucosphyrus* group of mosquitoes [94, 95]. Since the identification of a large number of human infections with *P. knowlesi* in Malaysian Borneo in 2004, sporadic cases have been reported from countries including the Philippines, Thailand, Vietnam, Cambodia, Myanmar, Singapore, Brunei, India, Indonesia and China and *P. knowlesi* is now the most common cause of human malaria in areas of Malaysian Borneo (Figure 4) [96-112]. Recent molecular studies have additionally identified human infections with *P. cynomolgi*, another primate malaria species carried by macaques, within these same regions [54].

Figure 4. Reports of PCR confirmed *P. knowlesi* cases by country from 1996 – 2014 (data obtained from [113] and aggregated by country)

Molecular studies indicate *P. knowlesi* is not a newly emergent malaria species and likely predates human settlement in Southeast Asia [114]. *P. knowlesi* was first described in macaques in the 1930s and the first naturally acquired human case was reported in 1965 in peninsular Malaysia [115, 116]. Subsequent epidemiological investigations of people residing within the area where this individual was infected did not identify any additional *P. knowlesi* cases in people, although *P. knowlesi* was detected in two out of the four long-tailed macaques screened [117]. No further natural infections were reported until 2004, when the application of molecular diagnostic tools identified a large focus of *P. knowlesi* infections in the Kapit division of Sarawak in Malaysian Borneo [112]. Retrospective studies have since detected *P. knowlesi* infections from archival blood films collected in the mid-1990s in Malaysia and Thailand, suggesting that previous human infections were misdiagnosed as other species by microscopy [118, 119].

Land use changes, resulting in increased spatial overlap between people, macaques and mosquitoes, have been proposed as the main driver of this apparent emergence [95, 114, 120]. In Northern Sabah, Malaysia, village-level *P. knowlesi* incidence was positively associated with both forest cover

and historical forest loss [121]. Analyses of clinical cases have found proximity to deforestation is associated with increases in reported *P. knowlesi* incidence and changes in the distribution of mosquito vectors, macaques and people at risk [95, 121, 122]. As well, agricultural activities and forest use have been identified as risk factors for individuals residing within these areas and mathematical modelling suggests increased contact between these individuals and macaque populations may drive transmission [55, 75, 123]. While human to human *P. knowlesi* transmission has been demonstrated experimentally, genetic studies and mathematical models suggest transmission remains primarily zoonotic [114, 124]. Further research is needed to monitor how ecological changes impact *P. knowlesi* transmission and human disease risks.

Box 3. Identifying relevant spatial scales to assess linkages between land use and disease risks

P. knowlesi risks vary substantially over small areas, driven by ecological changes and the behaviour and distribution of macaque, mosquito and human populations. A multidisciplinary research programme (MONKEYBAR, <http://malaria.lshtm.ac.uk/MONKEYBAR>) was established to investigate these complex linkages between *P. knowlesi* and land use change in Sabah and to assess opportunities for disease prevention and control. This project conducted integrated entomology, primatology and social science studies in addition to larger epidemiological population studies, including a case control study and ecologically stratified cross sectional surveys [75].

Detailed spatial data on mosquito biting rates and human and macaque movements highlighted differences in the importance of habitats for different species over distance. To better understand these factors, data driven approaches can identify how the predictive ability of landscape variables changes by spatial scale [125, 126]. Models incorporating data at multiple spatial scales can outperform single-scale models and generate new insights by describing spatial scale scales of landscape variable influence (Figure 5 [126]). For example, analysis of land cover and use characteristics at different buffer radii around households (Figure 5a) show changes in the relationship between disease occurrence and forest cover (b), fragmentation (c) and population densities (d). Figure 5e illustrates the probability of disease occurrence based on two variables analysed at different scales; based on these environmental and demographic variables, boosted regression trees were then used to develop risk maps of disease occurrence for the study site (f).

Figure 5. Effects of landscape and demographic variables at different spatial scales on the probability of *P. knowlesi* occurrence in Northern Sabah Malaysia based on household locations of reported cases and uninfected individuals (Brock et. al, unpublished): a. Extraction of forest cover data derived from satellite data at different buffer radii surrounding household, b. Marginal effect curve of proportion of forest cover within a 5km radius on probability of disease occurrence showing increased amounts of forest cover associated with higher probability of disease occurrence, c. Marginal effect curve of forest fragmentation (as measured by the perimeter-area ratio) within 5km radius on disease occurrence probability, d. Marginal effect curve of population density within 2km radius showing lower risks of disease at higher population densities, e. Probability of disease occurrence by percentage of forest cover within 0.05 km and forest loss

within 5km, f. Predictions of probability of disease occurrence using environmental predictors at multiple spatial scales

In areas of rapid ecological change, understanding and controlling disease requires both empirical statistical mapping approaches and transmission modelling on mechanisms giving rise to spatial and temporal risk patterns. This work highlights the importance of assessing spatial risks based on combinations of detailed mapping of disease dynamics and identification of environmental risk factors from population-based studies.

4.2 *P. simium* and *P. brasilianum* in South America

Similarly, within the South American rainforests, a human infection with the simian malaria *P. simium* had been historically reported, although there was little evidence of widespread human infections until recently [93]. Since 1993, sporadic human cases of a *P. vivax*-like malaria infection were reported from the Atlantic forest region of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, an area in which malaria had previously been eliminated. Parasitological and molecular investigations of these infections revealed human cases of *P. simium*, including 28 confirmed cases in 2015 – 2016 [56]. Genetic analyses showed similarities between these human infections and infections in the natural hosts, brown howler monkeys (*Alouatta clamitans*) present within the same region [56]. Phylogenetic studies have also suggested the simian malaria *P. brasilianum* has a close evolutionary relationship with *P. malariae* and may present further risks of zoonotic malaria infections within these regions [57]. Naturally acquired human infections with *P. brasilianum* were confirmed in indigenous communities in the Venezuelan Amazon [127]. Further surveillance is needed to monitor how the risks of these zoonotic malaria species evolve with continuing land use and ecological changes.

5. Monitoring land use change to assess relationships with malaria

LULCC analysis techniques are used to monitor physical changes to the environmental and the modification and management of these surfaces [2]. Geospatial data can be acquired from different sources, such as satellite-based remote sensing, aerial surveys and ground-based Global Positioning System (GPS) mapping (e.g. [128-133]). Frequently, analysis methods classify data obtained from these sources into discrete land cover classes relevant to the ecological processes of interest, such as forest cover or loss [134-136]. These data can then be combined with data on disease to identify environmental risk factors and predict future malaria risks.

5.1 Satellite-based remote sensing

Satellite-based remote sensing is widely used to obtain data on land cover, vegetation, rainfall, land surface temperatures and other environmental data for use in epidemiological studies [128]. These data have varying spatial and temporal resolutions, based on the pixel size of the data collected and how frequently the satellite covers a specific area. As well, remote-sensing data is characterised by spectral resolution, the number of wavelengths measured on the electromagnetic spectrum. Multispectral and hyperspectral imagery uses information beyond the visible range of the electromagnetic spectrum, allowing classification and transformation of imagery (such as for vegetation indices or estimates of surface moisture) [130]. Radar products, such as Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), scatterometer or radar altimeter, can be analysed to provide insight into structural properties and moisture content of land cover and can be analysed in combination with optical data from other sensors [137].

These earth observation data are available from a range of governmental and commercial agencies with varying characteristics (Table 2). While specifically tasking commercial satellites to obtain high resolution imagery for a specific time and site may be prohibitively expensive, freely available data is available through governmental and international agencies such as NASA (<https://eosps.nasa.gov/>) and European Space Agency (<https://www.esa.int/ESA>). An additional consideration is the technical knowledge, software and time required to process and analyse this data into a usable form. To better enable the use of these data, programmes such as Global Forest Watch (<https://www.globalforestwatch.org/>) publish processed data of forest cover and forest loss online, allowing download of imagery and email notifications of forest changes within regions of interest [8].

Additionally, cloud-based computing platforms such as Earth on Amazon Web Services (<https://aws.amazon.com/earth/>) and Google Earth Engine (<https://earthengine.google.com/>) provide access to imagery and infrastructure to analyse planetary-level data.

Table 2. examples of commonly used satellite remote-sensing data and derived products for land cover mapping

Parameter	Description	Resolution	Source
Elevation	Elevation (metres above sea level)	30 m	ASTER Global Digital Elevation Map [138]
Landsat 8	11 bands with wavelength 0.435-12.51 μm	15-100 m	NASA Landsat [139]
Sentinel-2	10 bands with wavelengths from 0.443 – 13.75 μm	10-60 m	European Space Agency [140]
Forest cover	Annual forest cover and forest loss (forest defined as over 50% canopy cover)	30 m	Derived from Landsat images, calculated by [8]
Intact forests	Undisturbed forest with minimum area of 50,000ha, minimum width of 10km, minimum corridor width of 2km	30 m	Obtained from Intact Forest Landscapes initiative, processed from Landsat [12]
Forest/ non-forest map	Forest/ non- forest map with forest classified as over 90% canopy cover with a minimum area of 0.5 ha	25 m	2015 global PALSAR-2/ PALSAR Forest/Non-Forest Map derived from Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) [141]
Global distribution of mangroves	Global mangrove distribution	30 m	UNEP, processed from 2011 GLS and Landsat data [142]
High resolution satellite imagery	Natural colour imagery of selected areas	6.5 m	RapidEye satellite data (imagery date July 2015) [143]

5.2 Aerial imagery

Although satellite-based remote sensing can cover large land areas, these data are often limited by the availability of imagery for a location and time and the high cost of specifically tasking satellites. High levels of cloud cover, a frequent issue in tropical areas, can additionally limit the usefulness of optical data sources. Alternatively, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs or drones) are increasingly

utilised to capture fine-scale data on landscape changes [144]. UAVs allow the collection of highly spatially resolute data at user-defined intervals and can be used to monitor forest deforestation, agricultural activities or population movements (e.g. [144-146]). For example, UAVs were used to map changes to macaque and mosquito habitats during forest clearing activities to evaluate how environmental changes affect human exposure to *P. knowlesi* [144]. Low-cost UAVs have additionally been developed to identify larval habitats for malaria control programmes in Tanzania [147]. While until recently most commercially available UAVs had limited spectral resolution, new multispectral and thermal cameras are progressively more affordable and available. In addition, sensors such as Lidar, frequently used on manned aircraft to measure forest structure, have been developed for UAVs [148, 149].

Figure 6. Examples of remote sensing data on landcover in Malaysian Borneo: a. false colour composite from LANDSAT satellite data (30m per pixel); b. very high resolution data collected by UAV (11 cm per pixel)

5.3 Habitat configuration

In addition to land cover and land use, increasing evidence illustrates landscape configuration can also modify disease transmission [30]. Fragmentation occurs when habitats become spatially separated due to land changes, creating a mosaic of land types. This increases the area of edges between different habitats and create ecotones, where previously separated populations are brought into closer contact and can increase disease incidence. For example, primate populations in highly fragmented forest areas have higher parasite infection levels, likely due to closer contact with other non-human primate groups and people [150-152]. Additionally, fragmentation may result in small patches with increased crowding and higher contact rates between hosts and populations. The increased density of birds within smaller forest patches has been associated with higher levels of tick

infestation, likely due to the higher probability of a tick finding a host [153]. These changes to landscape also lead to changes in microclimates within fragments and have been shown to impact mosquito densities [154, 155]. Numerous metrics have been used to describe these levels of fragmentation, measuring the patch density, edge lengths and ratio between edge and interior areas; these metrics can then be utilised with other land cover data to develop models of risk [156, 157].

5.4 Identifying environmental risk factors for malaria

Data on land cover, land use and habitat configuration can be combined with spatially explicit malaria data to identify risk factors for disease and predict how malaria burden may change with future environmental changes. Associations between environmental factors and human disease risks are modulated by the spatial scale of analysis; ecological processes affecting the distribution of people, disease vectors and wildlife hosts may occur at highly local to larger regional scales (see Box 3, [126]). For other vector-borne zoonotic diseases, variations in host richness and ecological community structure have been shown to be important at a fine spatial scale while changes in climate and other abiotic factors are more important across larger scales [158].

Malaria risk models have incorporated land use factors to develop spatially and/or temporal predictions of malaria risks, potentially allowing targeting of interventions and strategic planning. Outcome metrics for these models may range from incidence, infection and serological exposure prevalence in people to vectorial capacity and entomological inoculation rates [159]. Fine-scale data on parasite and human populations are available from resources such as the Malaria Atlas Project (<https://map.ox.ac.uk/>) and WorldPop (<http://www.worldpop.org.uk/>). Datasets on land cover, land use and associated characteristics (such as vegetation indices or land surface temperatures) are widely used to identify areas with increased risk [129, 160-163]. Data on landscapes and mosquito can be integrated with detailed behavioural and demographic risk determinants to explore plausible land use change scenarios and impacts on human health [164]. Multi-temporal data on LULCC and malaria can be further explored to evaluate how preventive measures and long term social and ecological changes may further impact risk [71, 76, 165]. In some cases, projected health burdens have been integrated into existing environmental impact assessment frameworks to enable the explicit consideration of malaria in land use decisions [166].

Understanding the potential implications of LULCC on malaria transmission can be used to guide mitigation measures for the potential health consequences of development projects. For example, during the plans for Batu Hijau, a large-scale surface mine in Indonesia, environmental assessments highlighted impacts on community malaria risks, particularly in relation to lagoons and potential vector breeding sites. This prompted the establishment of a corporate public health programme focussing on environmental management, larvicides, mosquito control and active and passive detection and treatment of malaria cases [167]. Similarly, health programmes were incorporated into projects led by ExxonMobil in Papua New Guinea and hydroelectric projects in Lao PDR to address negative externalities of developments [167]. The long-term success and consequences on local communities require further evaluation; however, the proactive identification and control of malaria risks illustrates how recognition of these changing risks can be practically applied.

6. Malaria elimination and LULCC

As a growing body of evidence suggests, the impacts of LULCC on malaria transmission are highly complex and context-specific. These anthropogenic environmental changes are driven by the need for resources, enabling increased income and food and water security. However, the ecological and demographic changes driven by these processes can create ideal habitats for malaria vectors and lead to greater populations at risk. Further, landscape changes can be driven by disruptions to existing socioeconomic systems, coupling with failures in health programmes to reduce capacity to detect and respond to changing malaria burdens.

Relationships between malaria transmission and LULCC are highly dependent on the spatial and temporal units of the data being analysed. Land use change is a dynamic process; initial impacts on disease transmission from disruption of existing ecosystems may change over time as transmission reaches new equilibrium states. Following deforestation, subsequent stages of forest succession and agricultural development may either create new habitats for disease vectors and hosts or lead to overall decreases in malaria burdens [31]. Monitoring these changes requires detailed data on malaria infection and disease burden, human, mosquito and other host distributions, relative to habitat types and collected in a consistent way to fully understand the long-term consequences of these changing environments on malaria. Research is also needed on how to implement interventions targeting high risk areas or populations, such as environmental management, border control in countries where malaria is eliminated or required malaria control plans alongside planned developments. Further research is needed to understand the complex effects of LULCC on malaria

risks and to develop disease surveillance and control methods appropriate to the local contexts and ecologies.

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